

Evaluation of urea forms in thaladi rice (IR20)

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We compared the performance of 75 kg N/ha as urea supergranules (USG), sulfur-coated urea (SCU), lac-coated urea (LCU), and gypsum-coated urea (Gyp-U) to split application (50% N basal, 25% N at tillering, and 25% N at panicle initiation) of prilled urea (PU). USG was point-placed at the center of 4 hills 2 d after transplanting. SCU, LCU,

and Gyp-U were broadcast and incorporated before planting.

P and K (22 kg P/ha, 42 kg K/ha) were applied basally. Soil was clay loam, low in available N, medium to high in available P and K contents. The trial was conducted during 1985-86 thaladi (Sep-Feb) with IR20 seedlings transplanted at 20- × 19-cm spacing. Grain yield was computed at 14% moisture.

SCU yielded over 1.9 t/ha more than control and gave 70 kg grain/kg N. All other forms of urea yielded more than split application of urea (see table). ☞

Comparative yield with different forms of urea in 1985-86 thaladi. Aduthurai, India.

Urea form	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Yield increase (t/ha)	N efficiency (kg grain/kg N)
Control	3.36 b	—	—
PU	4.34 a	0.98	58
USG	4.84 a	1.48	65
SCU	5.26 a	1.90	70
LCU	4.44 a	1.08	59
Gyp-U	4.40 a	1.04	59

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.

Response of Magsanaya upland rice in an acidic upland area to lime and fertilizer

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The effects on Magsanaya upland rice of lime and different kinds of fertilizer were studied in a split-plot design. Soil was an Ultisol, clay loam with pH 4.0, 4% organic matter, 6 ppm available P (Olsen), and 60 ppm H₂SO₄ extractable K.

Liming at 6 t/ha was assigned to the main plot. Different fertilizers were

Yield response of Magsanaya upland rice to lime and various fertilizers. Panay Island, Philippines.

Fertilizer	Yield ^a (t/ha)	
	No lime	6 t lime/ha
35-35-35 kg NPK/ha	2.20 b	2.30 a
28-28-28 kg NPK + 100 kg commercial organic fertilizer	2.08 b	2.02 b
28-28-28 kg NPK + 1.8 t bat cave rock phosphate mixed with bagasse ash	2.50 a	2.43 a
10 t dried chicken dung	1.17 c	1.39 c
20 t fresh azolla	0.54 d	.86 d
No fertilizer	0.43 d	.72 d
CV (%)	Main Plot —	12.81 (ns)
	Subplot —	6.3 (s.)

^aSeparation of means by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level.

assigned to the subplots (see table).

Lime, chicken dung, and azolla were broadcast and incorporated 1 mo before planting. Other fertilizers were applied just before planting.

Applying lime did not significantly increase yield. Chicken dung and azolla were not as good as commercial NPK, either alone or in mixture (see table). ☞

Rice-Based Cropping Systems

A suitable cropping system for Thambiraparanj region in Tamil Nadu

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In Thambiraparanj region of Tirunelveli District in Tamil Nadu, a two-crop system — a short-duration rice during first season (Jun-Sep) and a medium-duration rice during second season (Oct-Feb) — is generally followed. We conducted an experiment to find a suitable three-crop system, by raising a

third crop of pulses and oil seeds during summer depending on available soil moisture and summer showers. We tested five crops (Table 1).

Black gram, green gram, and soybean seeds were dibbled without land preparation and groundnut seeds were dibbled after land preparation. Spacing was 30 cm between rows for all, and 10 cm between plants for black gram and soybean and 15 cm for green gram and groundnut. Seed rate was 20 kg/ha for black gram and soybean, 37.5 kg/ha for green gram, and 100 kg/ha for groundnut. Gingelly seeds were broadcast after land preparation at

Table 1. Crops tested in the summer season, 1984-85, Paddy Experiment Station, Ambasamuduram, Tamil Nadu, India.

Crop	Variety	Duration (d)	Sowing date
Black gram (<i>Vigna mungo</i>)	Co. 5	76	17 Feb 1985
Green gram (<i>Vigna radiata</i>)	Co. 4	92	17 Feb 1985
Soybean (<i>Glycine max</i>)	Co. 1	94	17 Feb 1985
Groundnut (<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>)	Co. 2	112	19 Feb 1985
Gingelly (<i>Sesamum indicum</i>)	Co. 1	96	6 Mar 1985

5 kg/ha. Rainfall during the crop season (Feb-Jun) was 104 mm but only 32 mm was received within 42 d after sowing.

Table 2 shows the mean grain yield in a decreasing order of 0.53 t for black gram, 0.41 t for soybean, 0.33 t for groundnut, 0.28 t for green gram, and 0.21 t/ha for gingelly. Better performance of black gram was ascribed to its shorter duration, uniform and synchronous flowering, and completion of harvest in two pickings. The results indicated that a third crop of pulse would fit in a commonly used two crop rice - rice rotation. *S*

Table 2. Grain yield of first, second, and third crops during 1984-85, Paddy Experiment Station, Ambasamuduram, Tamil Nadu, India.

Cropping pattern	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	First crop	Second crop	Third crop
TKM9-IR20-Black gram	4.52	4.11	0.53
TKM9-IR20-Green gram	4.38	4.18	0.28
TKM9-IR20-Soybean	4.33	4.26	0.41
TKM9-IR20-Gingelly	4.57	4.07	0.21
TKM9-IR20-Groundnut	4.28	4.11	0.34
IR20-ADT36-Black gram	3.28	3.34	0.52
IR20-ADT36-Green gram	3.17	3.37	0.27
IR20-ADT36-Soybean	3.08	3.45	0.40
IR20-ADT36-Gingelly	3.04	3.47	0.20
IR20-ADT36-Groundnut	3.05	3.70	0.32
CD (5%)	0.41	0.55	-

Organic manures as a nitrogen source in a rice - wheat rotation

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The effect of poultry, piggery, and farmyard manures as substitute N was evaluated at the PAU farm during kharif 1984 and 1985. The soil (pH 8.5, EC 0.15 dS/m, organic C 0.25%, total N 0.03%) of the experimental field is loamy sand (Typic Ustochrept) with an average percolation rate of 5 mm/h. The rice variety was PR106.

Poultry, piggery, and farmyard manures containing 1.50, 1.36, and 0.51% N were applied at 5.0, 5.5, and 15 t/ha, each adding about 75 kg N/ha. The manures also were supplemented with 2 levels (80 and 120 kg N/ha) of urea N applied in 3 equal splits: at transplanting and at 21 and 42 d after transplanting. A basal dose of 13 kg P and 12.5 kg K/ha was applied at last puddling.

Yields with poultry manure without fertilizer N were twice as high as those with other manures (see figure). With fertilizer N, poultry manure also outyielded farmyard and piggery manures. Yields with poultry manure and 80 kg N/ha were as high as those with 160 kg N/ha alone. Yields with farmyard and piggery manures and 80 kg N/ha were almost equal to those with 120 kg N/ha alone. The results

Rice yields with organic manures substituting for N (mean of 2 yr).

suggest that substituting organic manure for 40 to 80 kg fertilizer N/ha is feasible, depending upon the nature of the organic manure.

The residual effects of these manures on a following wheat crop (with 90 kg N and 13 kg P/ha underdose) also were compared. With poultry manure applied to the previous rice crop, wheat yield was 1180 kg/ha more; with farmyard

manure, 770 kg/ha more; with piggery manure, 660 kg/ha more. These yields were comparable to yield with the recommended 120 kg N and 26 kg P/ha applied to the wheat crop. Results indicate that application of any one manure to rice gives a residual effect equivalent to 30 kg N and 13 kg P/ha in wheat. Poultry manure had the largest residual effect. *S*